

Original Research Article

Impact of Mobile Phone Usage on the Learning Activities of University Students

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Abstract

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Mobile phones play a significant role as a new technology used for the communication in our everyday routine of the individual and their social life. Mobile phones practice affects the assertiveness, morals, ethics, principles and the performances of the university student because of the excess use of phones in their daily life. Students with excess usage of mobile phones have low GPAs as they are giving more time to the mobile phones. The study found that young people have consistently shown higher levels of attachment to their mobile phones. The Purpose of the study was to identify the impact of mobile phones on the learning activities of the University students. The objectives of the study was to investigate the perceived ease of use of smartphones by students in learning activities, Measure the perceived utility of a smartphone in the academic performance of students, to explore the effect of smartphone use on student learning activities. The design is to conduct this study the Quantitative descriptive cross sectional study design was used. This study was conducted in the University of Lahore. The target population for this study consisted of 250 students Questionnaire was used to collect the data. The questionnaires were administered by using convenient sampling. Data were statistically analyzed on SPSS version 21 and inferential statistics. The results of this study showed that the use of smartphones has a positive effect on the learning activities of students in a way that they can easily share lectures with colleagues and record and store all lecture material delivered by the teacher. It also helps in quick access to online information. Easy contact and communication with friends. The study also explored the negative influence of excess use of smartphones on the students' learning activities, such as students use more social networking sites and play games which diverts student's attention from studies and leads to decreased academic performance. Calls and messaging distract students during lecture hours. Students should be made aware of and informed by teachers and parents on the frequency, number of hours or time spent on cell phone use and affect academic performance. Future research should concentrate on ways to promote learners' deliberate actions towards using smartphones in order to improve the ability to use smartphones to maximize learning performance.

Keywords: Impact, Mobile Phone, Learning Activities, University Students

INTRODUCTION

Mobile phones play a significant role as a new technology used for the communication in our everyday routine of the individual and their social life. Mobile phones are the

major developed technology nowadays. Mobile phones practice affects the assertiveness, morals, ethics, principles and the performances of the university student

because of the excess use of phones in their daily life. Mobile phones have improved the competences of university students in education activities by connecting with the internet for interrelating lectures, sharing files and online activities in the university. (Njagi and Silas, 2016).

Some other research demonstrates that excess use of mobile phones has an adverse effect on the educational activities of the students. Students with excess usage of mobile phones have low GPAs as they are giving more time to the mobile phones. Mobile phones are the source of communication, for sharing information and thoughts. For these features, mobiles are becoming a necessary part of our daily life (Rabiu et al., 2016). One of the world's fastest-growing emerging technologies is the mobile phone. Cell phones have become more accessible; teenagers increasingly own and use them. The study found that young people have consistently shown higher levels of attachment to their mobile phones, which due to the time conducted to the phones could serve as distractions for them. British studies have found that more and more individuals are becoming addicted to their mobile phones, causing discomfort and irritability. (Ezemenaka, 2013).

According to Darko-Adjei (2019). Almost every facet of human life has been dramatically changed by the advent of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and Net services. Actually, the way of teaching and learning is very straightforward. The creation of smartphones and their associated devices has dramatically changed teaching and learning globally. Smartphone users' dramatic rise has also accelerated the development of mass media operators. It was also indicated in a survey that nearly 60% of the world's population had contact with cell phones.

According to (Pradhan, 2020). For many young people, the smartphone is a status symbol nowadays. The appearance of the handset, functionality and modified accessories showed the status of their phone, and 60% of teenagers were willing to update their cell phone. The majority of researchers find that in schools and universities, cell phones contribute to problematic use. There is a conflict of interest between young people, parents and teachers over the use of mobile phones. Teachers are concerned about problems of discipline in the classroom, but they are concerned for parents to be in touch with their area at all times.

As well as university life and history, mobile phones are going to be an important part of our everyday life. In any possible campus environment, including the classroom, even an unplanned reflection of today's university students will show mobile phones existence used both openly and secretly. Despite rules against doing so, university learners often use the mobile throughout lecture time. The device seems to be proficient in contributing to student education and enhancing academic success as cell phone expertise

continues its speedy progress. Modern cell phones allow users, at almost any time and any location, to access a diversity of electronic media. (Hossain, 2019).

Ifeanyi and Chukwuere (2018). Mentioned in their study that high levels of smartphone addiction indicate that it impacts the academic performance of students. This addiction raises some questions as to whether the use of the hampers of smartphones or raises student output in general. The advent of cell phone technology has flourished with the quest for new changes in information and desire among university students, and most of them, including undergraduate students, are affected. This influence relates both negatively and positively to the academic success of the students.

According to (Darko-Adjei, 2019). The use of a Smartphone is not used for knowledge. The study shows that students have often been found to use their phones more for playing games and other social events than for studying. It was also observed that students often use cellphones on social media sites such as Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram etc. rather than using it for informative purposes, considering the extraordinary aids of the phone in education.

Advanced features of the mobile phones impending to decrease the responsiveness of the student in their classes and learning activities. Mobile phones improve the educational activities of the students by contributing learning. Latest research proposes that students take mobile phones for relaxation as they use mobile for playing games, social networking, photography, texting, messaging and watching videos. Mobile phones are interrupting the educational activities of the students as they are using phones for leisure instead of education. (Njagi and Silas, 2016). It is important to notice in the same study that there are more cell phone users in developing countries related to progressive ones, which means that the more developed countries use smartphones. The mobile phone has also made the lives of students relaxed, as they can get their data on the computer through electronic learning and mobile learning. (Darko-Adjei, 2019).

According to (Pradhan, 2020). There is a clear link between the excess use of cell phones by teenagers for entertainment and decreased academic performance. Research also notes that students get less sleep and skip their classes by using the internet late at night. The WHO has reported that mobile phone overuse possibly contributes to wellbeing hazards and has listed mobile phone radioactivity as a human poison.

Gikas and Grant (2013). Conducted a study which shows that 67% of students agree that cell phones are significant for their academic performance and they use their phones for academic activities. As an educational strategy, the increased omnipresence of mobile has the potential to generate new possibilities for advanced education students and to explore connectivity and social media. Mobile phones can provide learners with

informative prospects to access course material, as well as to connect wherever they are located with instructors and student colleagues.

According to (Miah, 2017). students often report using a diversity of electric media during class, learning, and doing homework, including mobile phones. Many studies have established an adverse association among multitasking and academic success using a variety of approaches. Firstly, the impact of multitasking with a collection of electronic media on the capability of students to benefit from traditional addresses in the university classroom was evaluated.

Purpose

The purpose of the study is to identify the impact of mobile phone on the learning activities of the University students.

Significance of the study

The significance of research is to describe the positive and negative impact of cell phones on the learning activities and theoretical performance of university students. The study gives awareness about the excess use of mobile phones and how they affect human life in different ways. By increasing health risks, lower their academic performance, distracting their learning process, developing psychologically problems. The results obtained in this study could be used by other researchers for further research study.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to (Darko-Adjei, 2019). The smartphones help students interact with their peers and masters/tutors in their classes. To illustrate the details, diagrams, and concepts with colleagues, students also use smartphones. In this study, it was pointed out that mobile phones help the educational activities of students in different ways, such as uploading study ingredients, recording live lectures, assisting in research work and performing assignments. It was noted that students often use cell phones on social media sites rather than using it for informative purposes, which decreases the academic performance of students.

According to lfeanyi and Chukwuere (2018). The use of smartphones for learners has both a negative and a positive impact. In addition, the researcher highlights the negative side of the coin, where the mobile has developed a major study diversion. For example, if not strictly monitored, there is a high tendency for students attached to their mobile phone to check, inform or alert almost every minute. Consequently, this distracts their

attention from their research, even when a lecturer is at the height of teaching at a lecture period. According to Hossain (2019). Modern mobile phones allow users, at almost any time and any location, to access a variety of electronic media. With most mobile phones, common activities such as playing video games, browsing the Net, and tracking social media sites are now all simply achieved. Researchers have related each of these behaviours to academic success, independent of mobile phone use.

According to (Hossain, 2019). Lower GPAs have been associated with heavy video game play and excess use of social media, for instance. Academic performance increased by Less use of the internet.

Frimpong, Asare, and Otoo-Arthur (2016). Conducted a study in which he investigates the impact of text on student educational consequences have focused on the theory of information processing as a basis to argue that text can cause disruptions that obstruct knowledge of students.

According to (Miah, 2017). Showed that the students that spend their most of the time on social media like Facebook, they have lower GPA than non-users. Similarly, a solid, adverse association between time spent on Facebook and actual increasing GPA was found by some researchers.

According to (Miah, 2017). The populations around the world show the negative relationships with excess use of mobile phone and lower academic performance have been discovered.

Cumaoglu (2015). Discussed in his study of mobile learning leads positively to the success of students. The use of mobile phones outside the classroom is often considered to be useful for learning. Students make their own educational network via mobile devices and convey out messaging and societal networking events with their friends and teachers. It was also noted that teachers use mobile phones favorably with regard to the writing skills of students with exceptional informative needs. It can also be argued that students with altered informative needs can profit from mobile phones through numerous resources.

Frimpong et al. (2016). Research has shown that 62 per cent of the programs available to students on their laptops are thought to be distracting. In addition, the researchers found that instant messaging was negatively related to quiz averages, project grades, and final exam grades, and was of specific interest to the current study.

According to Lee, Cho, Kim, and Noh (2015). Excessive use of smartphones has made mobile addiction seem to be a social issue. In everyday life, the user of smartphone addiction was nervous and anxious without a smartphone and they suffered the symptoms that people were unable to avoid using a smartphone and it contributes to daily life problems (Iqbal and Ahmed Bhatti, 2015). Discuss in this study that Among young people, smartphones are increasingly

becoming popular. In developed countries, smartphone penetration among young people aged 18-24 is 72 percent. Young people in developing countries are catching the wave quickly, primarily due to the market availability of low-cost Android-based smartphones.

Lee et al. (2015). Conducted a study which showed the prevalence of smartphone addiction was 11.1 percent from 10 to 49 years of age. Therefore, the incidence of smartphone addiction was actually higher than last year (2.7 percent). In particular, on 20s who were typically leaning in daily than other generations, there were high addiction rates. The addiction rate for the 20s was 13.6 percent. The level of smartphone addiction can impact learning for students who have spent much of their daily lives studying.

(Alzougool and AIMansour, 2017). found that in general, each student had 80 apps on their smartphone, and 16% of the apps were used for some kind of learning. On average, students pass five hours a day on their cell phones, connecting with others via social networking sites, and remaining available for around 16 hours a day. There can also be harmful effects on users and the environment, such as interruption of social interactions, sleep loss and attention deficits, in addition to the advantages of using a smartphone. Over use of mobile phones also causes lower academic performance of students.

According to (Rabiu et al., 2016). indicates that the use of cell phones adversely impacts the academic performance of students. This suggests that there is a low GPA for students who use cell phones more. There is a low GPA for students who use cell phones for almost 7-10 hours and those who use mobile phones during most of their classes.

A study conducted by Singh and Samah (2018). Stated that Smartphone use and misuse in the environment of college lectures. The result reveals that students do not focus on their lecturer in their class because they spend so much time on texting. Students who used cell phones were lower in the class score than students who did not use mobile phones and were unable to recall any of the results of the lectures. The use of cell phones distracts students from learning, and students assume that learning in the classroom is interrupted during texting.

According to (Cui, 2014). Mobile phone media split time restrictions, shift the way student's exchange, and provide students with interactive, individualized counseling and different learning styles. Mobile phone media to minimize physical space, but also likely to extend students' distance of mind, inhibit emotional preparation. However, excessive exposure to online media can lead to "Internet addiction syndrome" resulting in a variety of physical illnesses. Mobile networks to spread, students with easy-to-weak contact information can be distracted by learning effort, poor academic

results, over-indulgence, which may also give up normal studies.

According to (Alaba, 2011). There was no question that the advent of a mobile communication system had a positive and negative effect on education. Developing countries are embracing mobile technology with enthusiasm. However, the excitement quickly started to fade away as a result of a multitude of problems associated with students' use of cell phones. Any of the issues are: discipline, malpractice testing and mobile abuse.

According to Ng, Hassan, Nor, and Malek (2017). Cell phones are not used only for text and calling purposes. But also, for internet surfing. This certainly leads to failure of academic record. Students having less GPA are found more users of smartphones than others students who comparatively use less smartphones.

According to (Santhi and Rajesh). Any new technology, young people, were the first to be introduced to it. Smartphones are changing the way they interact with each other and they also play a crucial role in their academic and social lives. Overuse of cell phones and Internet connectivity makes it possible to see the effects of young people's academic success and lifestyle, as well as the diversion and disruption of their academic work. It leads to a persistent downward trend in academic activity, a spike in dropout cases, major failures in the test, and even a malpractice in the examination with the aid of a mobile phone.

According to (Santhi and Rajesh). Heavy use of technology by teenagers for leisure purposes is strongly associated with decreased academic performance. Study also says that using the internet late in the night lets them sleepless and skip school. A study of youth patterns found that 68 per cent of students earned low academic qualifications who owned a cell phone. WHO has stated that overuse of mobile phones does indeed pose health hazards and has listed cell phone radiation as carcinogenic to humans.

According to (Frimpong et al., 2016). It claimed that the use of cell phones has increased so dramatically that it has become one of the most influential forces on society in today's world. Study the impact of cell phone use on the academic performance of students. Students using cellphones in classrooms, 93.5 percent used mobile phones during school hours, with 91.8 percent using mobile phones in classrooms to boost their knowledge of understudy topics. Also, 80.5 percent were distracted by phone during classes, in the form of social media visits (31.1 per cent), text messages (27.6 per cent) and calls received (25.6 percent).

According to (Khan et al., 2015). Usually, Students of university use Cell phones for communication. Almost every university student has one or more cell phones. They affect their social activity, their health and their budget. The results of the survey indicate that around 60 per cent of students claimed that mobile devices were

used as a source of unfair means in the examination hall. This means that cell phones have a negative influence on students. Cell phones are an important source of entertainment for students. If the time allocated to entertainment is raised, so the student's time is lost. 52% of university students think cell phones are a waste of time for university students.

METHODOLOGY

Research design

To conduct this study, the Quantitative descriptive cross-sectional design is used.

Place of work

The research is conducted in the university of Lahore.

Target Population

The target population in this study consists of 250 university students.

Sample size

To calculate the sample size use solvin, s formula.

$$N = N/1 + N(e)^2$$

$$n = 250/1 + 250(0.05)^2$$

$$n = 250/1 + 250(0.0025)$$

$$n = 250/1 + 0.6$$

$$n = 250/1.6$$

$$n = 156$$

So, the study sample is the 156 participants.

Data collection

Data were collected through questionnaire distributed among participants

Inclusion criteria

University students, Students that are present during data collection, Students that are agree to take part in the study.

Exclusion criteria

Participants who refuse to fill questionnaires, Students absent at the time of data collection., Visitors and

workers excluded from the study.

Ethical consideration

Ethical consideration is preferred in this research. For this purpose, the permission is obtained from the ethical committee of the University of Lahore. The sufficient information about this research is given to the participants that they can give their consent. The consent is attained through a letter. Students are given the right of autonomy and the nature and the purpose of the study is to inform prior to the implementation of any action. Participants have the right to leave the study participation at any time. Participants are taken in confidence that all the collected information and records remain confidential.

Study instrument

The questionnaire was adopted from the study conducted by (Darko-Adjei, 2019). The questionnaire included 20 questions.

Data Analysis

SPSS version 21 was used to analyze the data.

Results and Data analysis

In this research 156 questionnaires were delivered to the students. It includes the demographic data and mobile phone effect on students learning. Data was collected and put on SPSS version 21 for analysis. Applied frequency test on different variables calculated and graphically portrayed in table and graphs.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The aim of present study was to assess the impact of mobile phone usage on the learning activities of university students. The objectives of this research are to investigate the perceived ease of use of smartphones by students in learning activities and Measure the academic performance of students who overuse cell phones. And also explore the effect of smartphome use on student learning activities. The quantitative research results were critically analyzed by the inferential statistic and discuss the response of the participant. The participants of this study are university students. The ages of participants range between (20-25) 55.8% and (26-30) are 29.5% and (31-35) 9.8% and between (36-40) are 5.1%. Most of the participants who take part in this study were female 58.3% and 41.7% were male. The participants who are in

Table 1. Demographic information of participants

S. No			Frequency	Percent
1.1	Age	20-25	87	55.8%
		26-30	46	29.5%
		31-35	15	9.6%
		36-40	8	5.1%
		Total	156	100%
1.2	Gender	Male	65	41.7%
		Female	91	58.3%
		Total	156	100%
1.3	Educational year	1 st year	19	12.2%
		2 nd year	43	27.6%
		3 rd year	51	32.7%
		4 th year	43	27.6%
		Total	156	100%

Table 2. The impact of mobile phone usage on the learning activities of students

S. No	Questions		Frequency	Percentage
2.1	Smartphones enable me to take quiz and Interim Assessment (IA) anywhere and anytime.	Strongly disagree	2	1.3%
		Disagree	8	5.1%
		Neutral	10	6.4%
		Agree	110	70.5%
		Strongly agree	26	16.7%
		Total	156	100%
2.2	It helps me in quick access to information Online.	Strongly disagree	3	1.9%
		Disagree	5	3.2%
		Neutral	7	4.5%
		Agree	90	57.7%
		Strongly agree	51	32.7%
		Total	156	100%
2.3	Using the smartphone for learning has enabled me to gain extra skills and experiences outside the classroom.	Strongly disagree	4	2.6%
		Disagree	8	5.1%
		Neutral	20	12.8%
		Agree	96	61.5%
		Strongly agree	28	17.9%
		Total	156	100%
2.4	Smartphone enable me to easily receive notification when announcement is posted	Strongly disagree	4	2.6%
		Disagree	3	1.9%
		Neutral	13	8.3%
		Agree	105	67.3%
		Strongly agree	31	19.9%
		Total	156	100%

Table 2. Continue

2.5	Smartphone enable me to record lectures delivered by my tutors	Strongly disagree	1	0.6%
		Disagree	7	4.5%
		Neutral	17	10.9%
		Agree	106	67.9%
		Strongly agree	25	16%
		Total	156	100%
2.6	I can easily access my e-mail using smartphone.	Strongly disagree	2	1.3%
		Disagree	5	3.2%
		Neutral	7	4.5%
		Agree	102	65.4%
		Strongly agree	40	25.6%
		Total	156	100%
2.7	Smartphones helps me to store all my lecture materials.	Strongly disagree	4	2.6%
		Disagree	4	2.6%
		Neutral	15	9.6%
		Agree	100	64.1%
		Strongly agree	33	21.2%
		Total	156	100%
2.8	Smartphones help me in sharing lecture materials among colleagues.	Strongly disagree	1	0.6%
		Disagree	6	3.8%
		Neutral	10	6.4%
		Agree	102	65.4%
		Strongly agree	37	23.7%
		Total	156	100%
2.9	Smartphones enable me to use social media platforms for class activities.	Strongly disagree	3	1.9%
		Disagree	12	7.7%
		Neutral	21	13.5%
		Agree	98	62.8%
		Strongly agree	22	14.1%
		Total	156	100%
2.10	Smartphones enable me to schedule my lecture activities with reminders.	Strongly disagree	1	0.6%
		Disagree	6	3.8%
		Neutral	27	17.3%
		Agree	106	67.9%
		Strongly agree	16	10.3%
		Total	156	100%
2.11	I always use my smartphones more for playing games and accessing social media platforms instead of using it for learning	Strongly disagree	10	6.4%
		Disagree	43	27.6%
		Neutral	31	19.9%
		Agree	57	36.5%
		Strongly agree	15	9.6%
		Total	156	100%
2.12	Smartphones can potentially increase multitasking and task switching during academic activities leading to decrease in academic performance.	Strongly disagree	5	3.2%
		Disagree	17	10.9%
		Neutral	42	26.9%
		Agree	82	52.6%
		Strongly agree	10	6.4%
		Total	156	100%

Table 2. Continue

2.13	Smartphone takes more of my attention from studies.	Strongly disagree	3	1.9%
		Disagree	23	14.7%
		Neutral	37	23.7%
		Agree	74	47.4%
		Strongly agree	19	12.2%
		Total	156	100%
2.14	Sometimes I am not able to pay attention in class because of my smartphone.	Strongly disagree	8	5.1%
		Disagree	30	19.2%
		Neutral	21	13.5%
		Agree	76	48.7%
		Strongly agree	21	13.5%
		Total	156	100%
2.15	Using smartphone for learning consumes a lot of data bundle which increase my expenditure	Strongly disagree	4	2.6%
		Disagree	17	10.9%
		Neutral	53	34.0%
		Agree	66	42.3%
		Strongly agree	16	10.3%
		Total	156	100%
2.16	Smartphone usage in learning creates an isolation or a feeling of being out of the- loop for both instructors.	Strongly disagree	4	2.6%
		Disagree	23	14.7%
		Neutral	57	36.5%
		Agree	62	39.7%
		Strongly agree	10	6.4%
		Total	156	100%
2.17	The use of smartphone has put negative influence on student's ethical values	Strongly disagree	4	2.6%
		Disagree	17	10.9%
		Neutral	39	25%
		Agree	74	47.4%
		Strongly agree	22	14.1%
		Total	156	100%
2.18	Mobile phone use as a source of unfair means in examination hall by students.	Strongly disagree	2	1.3%
		Disagree	27	17.3%
		Neutral	36	23.1%
		Agree	69	44.2%
		Strongly agree	22	14.1%
		Total	156	100%
2.19	Mobile phone is responsible for low academic performance of students	Strongly disagree	3	1.9%
		Disagree	14	9%
		Neutral	33	21.2%
		Agree	74	47.4%
		Strongly agree	32	20.5%
		Total	156	100%
2.20	Mobile Phone usage diverts students during study time.	Strongly disagree	2	1.3%
		Disagree	4	2.6%
		Neutral	16	10.3%
		Agree	81	51.9%
		Strongly agree	53	34%
		Total	156	100%

1st year were 12.2% and 2nd year were 27.6% and most of the participants were in 3rd year 32.7% and 27.6% are in 4th year who filled the questionnaire. In this study 1.3% participants answer strongly disagree to: Smartphone enables them to take quiz and Interim Assessment (IA) anywhere and anytime and 5.1% participants disagree, 6.4% participants answer neutral, 70.5% participants answer agree and 16.7% participants answer strongly agree to the statement. 1.9% participants respond strongly disagree to: smartphone helps in quick access to online information and 3.2% participants disagree, 4.5% participants respond neutral, 57.7% participants respond agree and 32.7% participants strongly agree to the statement. 2.6% participants answer strongly disagree to: students learn extra skill and gain experience outside the classroom by using smartphone. 5.1% participants answer disagree, 12.8% participants answer neutral, 61.5% participants answer agree and 17.9% participants answer strongly agree to the statement. 2.6% participants answer strongly disagree to: students easily receive notification when announcement is posted and 1.9% participants answer disagree, 8.3% participants answer neutral, 67.3% participants answer agree and 19.9% participants answer strongly agree to the statement. 0.6% participants answer strongly disagree to: Smartphone help to record lectures delivered by my tutors and 4.5% participants disagree, 10.9% participants respond neutral, 67.9% participants answer agree and 16.0% participants strongly agree to the statement. 1.3% participants strongly disagree: students easily access their email by using smartphones. 3.2% participants disagree, 4.5% participants respond neutral, 65.4% participants respond and 25.6% participants strongly agree to the statement. 2.6% answer strongly disagree to: smartphones help students to store all their lecture material. 2.6% participants disagree, 9.6% participants respond neutral, 64.1% participants respond and 21.2% participants strongly agree to the statement. 0.6% answer strongly disagree to: Smartphone help in sharing lecture materials among colleagues. 3.8% participants disagree, 6.4% participants respond neutral, 65.4% participants answer agree and 23.7% participants strongly agree to the statement. 1.9% participants strongly disagree. Smartphones enable students to use social media platforms for class activities. 7.7% participants disagree, 13.5% participants respond neutral, 62.8% participants answer agree and 14.1% participants were strongly agreed. 0.6% participants strongly disagree: Smartphones help students to schedule lecture activities with reminder and 3.8% participants disagree, 17.3% participants respond neutral, 67.9% participants respond and 10.3% participants strongly agree. 6.4% participants strongly disagree: students use their phones for playing games and accessing social media platforms more than using it for learning. 27.6% participants disagree, 19.9% participants respond neutral, 36.5% participants answer agree and 9.6% participants strongly agreed. 3.2%

participants' answers strongly disagree: Smartphones can potentially increase multitasking and task switching during academic activities leading to decrease in academic performance. 10.9% participants disagree, 26.9% participants respond neutral, 52.6% answer agree and 6.4% participants strongly agreed. 1.9% participants answer strongly disagree to: Smartphones take more students attention from studies and 14.7% participants disagree, 23.7% participants respond neutral, 47.4% participants answer agree and 11.5% participants were strongly agreed. 5.1% participants strongly disagree: Sometimes students are not able to pay attention in class because of smartphones. 19.2% participants disagree, 13.5% participants respond neutral, 48.7% participants answer agree and 13.5% participants strongly agree to the statement. The 2.6% respondent's answer strongly disagrees. Smartphones consume a lot of data bundles which increase student's expenditure. 10.9% participants disagree, 34.0% respond neutral, 42.3% participants answer agree and 10.3% participants strongly agreed. 2.6% participants respond strongly disagree to: Smartphone usage in learning creates an isolation or a feeling of being out of the- loop for both instructors and 14.7% participants disagree, 36.5% participants respond neutral, 39.7% participants answer agree and 6.4% participants strongly agree to the statement. 2.6% participants strongly disagree: The use of smartphones has a negative influence on a student's ethical values. 10.9% participants disagree, 25.0% participants respond neutral, 47.4% participants answer agree and 14.1% participants strongly agreed. 1.3% participants strongly disagree: students use mobile phones as a source of unfair means in examination hall. 17.3% participants disagree, 23.1% participants respond neutral, 44.2% participants respond and 14.1% participants strongly agree to the statement. 1.9% participants respond strongly disagree to: Mobile phone is responsible for low academic performance of students and 9.0% participants disagree, 21.2% participants respond neutral, 47.4% participants answer agree and 20.5% participants were strongly agreed. 1.3% participants answer strongly disagree to: Mobile Phone usage diverts students during study time. 2.6% participants disagree, 10.3% participants respond neutral, 51.9% participants answer agree and 34.0% participants strongly agree to the statement (Khan et al., 2015). Conducted a study on the effect of cell phones on university students' grades. The results of the survey indicate that about 60 per cent of the respondents surveyed their view in support of the argument that in examination hall cell phones used as a source of unfair means. This shows that cell phones has a negative effect on university. Cell phones are a significant source of entertainment for students. If the entertaining time is raised, so the student's time is lost. The findings show that 52 percent of university students think cell phone is a waste of time for university students. When participants were asked about that mobile

phones help to better their academic performance and the effect of mobile phones on the quality of education of students, 46% replied 'agree,' 25% respond neutral and 29% disagree to the statement, and 42% of participants estimated that the quality of education is better with the use of mobile phones, while 39% disagree.

A study conducted by (Njagi and Silas, 2016). Students have demonstrated many aspects in which cell phones make it difficult for them to concentrate on their studies, such as wasting time on social media, disturbing their self-study, distracting them in class as they receive and attending text and calls. The cell phone also decreases the focus of students and diverts their attention from academic programmes. This suggests that students concentrate their attention on cell phone use while neglecting their academic activities.

A study conducted by (Ifeanyi and Chukwuere, 2018). participants were inquired about the use of mobile phones to help in the betterment of their academic performance or not; 76.3 per cent of students said it had increased moderately, 6.7 per cent said it had not increased, and the other 5.6 per cent indicated that their academic performance had certainly increased. (71.2 percent) indicates that they are usually distracted by smartphones. Smartphone use dominates the time of the participants, 29.6 percent of the students being sponsored. Overall, the use of smartphones lowers academic performance as indicated by 72.0 percent.

CONCLUSION

The purpose of the study is to identify the impact of mobile phones on the learning activities of the University students. The study followed a quantitative approach and exploratory design to analyse and describe the identified variables. Based on the present study it can be concluded that the use of smartphones has a positive effect on the learning activities of students in a way that they can easily share lectures with colleagues and record and store all lecture material delivered by the teacher. It also helps in quick access to online information. Easy contact and communication with friends. The study also explored the negative influence of excess use of smartphones on the students' learning activities, such as students use more social networking sites and play games which diverts student's attention from studies and leads to decreased academic performance. Calls and messaging distract students during lecture hours.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Such systems can be implemented by the Academic organizations which can forbid students from using social sites during the lectures.

- Students should be allowed to use their phones only when they are allowed by their teachers, like to access their learning activities.
- Students should be made aware of and informed by teachers and parents on the frequency, number of hours or time spent on cell phone use and affect academic performance.
- Future research should concentrate on ways to promote learners' deliberate actions towards using smartphones in order to improve the ability to use smartphones to maximize learning performance.
- Students of university should endeavor to make productive use of smartphones. They should do less focus on chatting and messaging to prevent their valuable time. So that this time could be utilized in their academic activities.
- should provide students with massive education about the benefits and drawbacks of using cell phones, as well as the safest way to use them. In addition, the organization should lay down strict rules and regulations to restrict the usage of cell phones during working hours.

LIMITATIONS

Unwillingness and hesitation of the participants were seen during collecting the data.

- The problem which I faced most of the time during the completing the questionnaire was limitation of time.
- Some participants refused to complete the personal information consent because they didn't want to appear their names and other personal information in the forms even though explaining that all the information was kept confidential.
- The study was conducted in a limited time period of 3 months
- The study was on small samples hence it cannot be generalized to a similar population of other areas.

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